

Applications of Electrophotocatalysis in C-H Functionalization of Organic Molecules.

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Dedicated to Miroslav Kozák

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Abstract: Electrophotocatalysis (EPC) has evolved as a new scientific discipline around the boundary of highly active fields: electrochemistry and photocatalysis. EPC allows us to combine the energy of light and electric potential to activate previously inaccessible compounds *via* single-electron transfer (SET). Herein, we review the most essential applications of EPC to the C-H functionalization of molecules. This work discusses mechanisms that can be encountered when designing such processes and analyzes technical aspects of performing EPC reactions in the laboratory.

1. Introduction

Processes based on single-electron transfer bring new, unique possibilities to activating small organic molecules. Injection of an electron usually leads to the weakening of some bonds, whereas abstraction of an electron generates new reactive electrophilic centers. Although stoichiometric chemical redox reagents can accomplish such electron transfer, redox processes can also be driven by external energy input. This has revolutionized the field of organic synthesis in the last 15 years, in the form of photo-redox catalysis,^[1] electrochemistry^[2] and mechanochemically-driven processes - piezoelectric catalysis^[3] and mechanical activation of charge-transfer complexes.^[4] Each of these processes has distinct advantages and disadvantages. Photo-redox catalysis usually occurs in a homogeneous phase, leading to low local concentrations of reactive species and lower chances of formation of byproducts. On the other hand, sacrificial

electron donors and oxidants are often required to close the photo-redox catalytic cycle, and the energy of a single photon limits the energetic input. Although methods combining more photons to perform a chemical transformation are known in nature (photosynthesis), such an approach requires very specific conditions in the laboratory, making it unsuitable for many substrates.^[5] Electrochemistry and mechanochemistry with piezoelectric materials occur at the phase interface, leading to a high relative concentration of reactive species. Reactivity in electrochemistry can be easily modulated by the applied potential, allowing for better selectivity control. As the mechanisms of photo-redox and electrochemical reactions are usually similar, merging these two types of activation is a logical step.^[6] Progress in this area has been hampered by the requirement for mastery of multiple different techniques and the requirement for relevant equipment for both processes. This is the reason applications of electrophotocatalysis (EPC) to synthetic organic chemistry are relatively recent.^[7] EPC allows us to take the best of both worlds: combining the energy of a photon with the redox potential, leading to super-reductants/-oxidants. Typical photo-redox reaction is performed using homogeneous photocatalysts, while a typical electrochemical process occurs in a heterogeneous environment at the electrode, even though exceptions exist in the form of heterogeneous photocatalysts (e.g. semiconductors) and mediated electrolysis. The synergy of photo- and electrochemistry also allows us to work in a homogeneous reaction system, using an electric current as the terminal oxidant/reductant, making the sacrificial reagents superfluous (Scheme 1).

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Michal Májek hails from Bratislava, Slovakia. He obtained his engineering degree from Institute of Chemical Technology in Prague, followed by PhD degree from the University of Regensburg, where he worked in group of Axel Jacobi von Wangelin. After finishing his postdoctoral stints with Kendall Houk at the UCLA and Robert Francke at University of Rostock, he moved back to Bratislava, where he started his own research group. His main research interest is development of new synthetic methods based on SET, and his hobby is science outreach.

Scheme 1. Merging photo-redox catalysis and electrochemistry for C-H functionalization reactions.

Many reactions developed in the infancy phase of photo-redox catalysis and electrochemistry, were intended to replace metal-catalyzed processes, where the metal acts as the redox-active center – such as cross-coupling reactions. By their nature, such reactions require pre-functionalization of starting materials by introducing weak C-X bonds, which then can be broken in the redox process. This introduces further steps into the synthesis and leads to the formation of stoichiometric waste products. The alternative to this approach is direct C-H functionalization.^[6] The main hurdle to a broader application of C-H functionalization is the innate stability of C-H bonds (BDEs over 400 kJ/mol). This translates to the high amount of energy required to break most C-H bonds: energy of 400 kJ/mol equals to a photon with a wavelength lower than 300 nm. This makes C-H functionalization a perfect candidate for processes where multiple sources of energy are used to activate the molecule, such as the EPC. Multiple research groups have successfully implemented EPC setups for C-H activation processes in recent years. There are three distinct strategies for a formal C-H activation of small organic molecules by EPC. In this review, we showcase how different EPC-enabled reactions utilize these strategies to form new bonds *via* C-H activation. Firstly, direct HAT process can be used as the key step to form reactive intermediate radicals, which undergo further transformations (Parts 4 and 5). Secondly, SET process can be used to form a reactive cation radical, containing highly acidic hydrogens that are easily deprotonated to form the intermediate radical (Part 6). Finally, intermediate radical can be formed by breaking C-X bonds (where X is not a hydrogen) in a redox process. The intermediate radical then reacts with aromatic systems, and the formal C-H activation occurs during re-aromatization (Part 7).

Scheme 2. Combining electrochemistry and photocatalysis; A – regeneration of the catalyst by electricity; B – enhancing the activity of doublet catalyst by its excitation; C – decoupled photo- and electro- chemical steps.

2. Combining Electrochemistry and Photocatalysis

The energy of light and electricity can be combined to ultimately perform a SET process in different modes. The simplest way in which photo-redox catalysis and electrochemistry can be merged is by using electricity to recycle the spent photocatalyst by turning it back to the original redox state. When net oxidative or net reductive processes are accomplished by photo-redox catalysis, a sacrificial electron acceptor or donor is required to

complete the catalytic cycle. Using sacrificial reagents means that the reaction mixtures become more complex, and a waste product is generated in a stoichiometric amount. Although this problem can be suppressed by using a sacrificial reagent that is converted to a useful product,^[9] this is impractical in most cases. Furthermore, sacrificial reagents can act in reactions other than electron transfer, leading to the formation of undesired byproducts.^[10] This contrasts with systems that use electric current as the terminal oxidant/reductant (Scheme 2A). Electrons are traceless reagents and, as such, superior to chemical redox reagents in this respect. When electricity is used to regenerate the photo-redox catalyst, the net charge has to be balanced by an electrochemical process at the counter electrode. Although this also potentially opens the door for undesired side reactions, this can be suppressed by using a divided cell or optimization of counter electrode material and size. These types of reactions usually do not require potential control as long as the photo-redox catalyst is depleted quickly (requiring efficient irradiation) and the current is kept sufficiently low.

To activate less reactive substrates, a feat important during development of C-H activation processes, electricity can be used to enhance the reactivity of photo-redox catalysts (Scheme 2B). Conceptually, this idea is derived from the photocatalytic con-PET process,^[11] but with electrochemistry radical ion of a photocatalyst can be obtained directly, following its excitation by light. In comparison with the con-PET process, high local concentrations of the charged photo-redox catalyst can be achieved close to the electrode, making the following excitation process more easily achievable. As a result, highly reactive super-reductant/-oxidant excited doublet species are prepared, which can activate substrates with redox potentials outside the window of traditional photo-redox catalysis. As the catalyst could be deactivated by a redox reaction at the counter electrode, divided cells are often required for this type of process, while electrolysis is performed at a controlled potential, as high applied voltage may lead to decomposition of starting materials.

Finally, light and electricity can be combined in one reaction sequence, yet without being intertwined in one catalytic cycle (Scheme 2C). This approach is commonly referred to as decoupled EPC,^[7h] and is the oldest known type of EPC with the first reported example from 1983.^[12] In this case, electrochemistry generates an intermediate **Int₁**, which is photoactive either by itself, or after a chemical transformation to another intermediate **Int₂**, followed by activation by light leads to its transformation to a final product. Ergo, photocatalysts are not used in this setup. While both electricity and light are required to form the desired products in decoupled electrochemistry, they perform two distinct reactions on different substrates, highlighting the difference from the first two examples of EPC.

3. Technical Aspects of EPC

When setting up an electrophotocatalytic reactor, multiple technical issues must be addressed: how the light is introduced into the system, the geometry of the reactor, and how the electric current will be supplied. Nowadays, three different visible light sources are common in photochemistry – single wavelength LEDs and broadband irradiation sources such as white LEDs and compact fluorescent lights (CFLs). Broadband irradiation sources

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can be useful during the catalyst/conditions screening phase when we are uncertain of which wavelength will be absorbed by the photoactive species. On the other hand, it is prudent to switch to single-wavelength LEDs when possible, as broadband irradiation can trigger undesired processes, and CFLs are even a source of highly energetic UV radiation.^[13] Electrodes provide electrical current, and their material significantly influences the reaction outcome.^[14] Glassy carbon is the commonly encountered anode material. In that case, platinum can often be used as the cathode (counter electrode), as hydrogen has a low overpotential on platinum, assuming that some source of protons is present in the reaction system. This allows to use a chemically non-interfering reaction, a hydrogen evolution, as the counter-reaction on the cathode. In some cases, the photoactive material has been successfully applied as the electrode material to join both the electrochemical and photochemical processes on the same element, the photoelectrode.

Scheme 3. Setups for EPC; PE = photoelectrode; CE = counter electrode.

The term Interfacial photoelectrochemistry (iPEC) refers to processes using such photoelectrochemical cells. This type of system can be applied to C-H activation processes of different complexity, ranging from oxygenations and aromatization reactions with oxygen,^[15] to more complex processes which we will discuss in more detail. In addition to the electrode material, its area can also influence the outcome of the electrochemical process.^[16] When using the same current, increasing electrode surface leads to lower current density, which generally equates to higher selectivity. Very large electrode areas can be accomplished using a carbon felt or wire mesh as one of the electrodes. The electrochemical cell itself can be either undivided, having a single electrolyte space for both anode and cathode or divided where products of electrolysis at anode and cathode do not mix, connected by a conductive spacer (Scheme 3B, frit, salt bridge). Although the use of divided cells can lead to a lower incidence of side reactions,^[17] this setup should not be used unless necessitated by low selectivity, as it leads to high ohmic resistance between the electrodes. This equates to a significant voltage drop, straining the capability of power sources, and it also leads to the formation of heat due to Ohmic losses, which has to be dissipated into the reaction system. Finally, electricity can be supplied at a constant current or constant potential. Setups with constant current are simpler as they require only two electrodes, and they can be used as long as a sufficiently low current density is applied and only one electroactive species is present in the system. Constant potential setup requires a more complex electrochemical cell, as another electrode (reference) has to be introduced into the system. In traditional electrosynthesis, constant potential setups lead to sluggish kinetics toward the completion of the reaction as the electroactive species is depleted, but this is generally not the case in EPC, as the catalyst concentration remains constant throughout the reaction. Finally, dedicated systems have been developed for EPC in flow. The short distance between electrodes in flow devices equates to a low ohmic drop. This type of setup leads to improved productivity

and allows for continuous processes to be developed.^[18] The requirement for irradiation close to a conductive surface (electrode) in small space of a flow reactor can be solved by using transparent conductive materials such as fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) or indium tin oxide (ITO) coated glass.^[19] Furthermore, micro-flow reactors for EPC can be manufactured by 3D-printing, making them accessible to a much broader audience and allowing for quick prototyping and screening of different reactor geometry.^[20]

4. EPC-Mediated C-H Functionalization By Direct HAT

The first section examines EPC-mediated C-H functionalization that relies on the direct hydrogen atom transfer (HAT) process provided by the irradiated photocatalyst, thus generating transient C-centered radical species. Metal mediators can be used in tandem reactions to activate the second substrate. In this case, the synergy of electro- and photocatalysis requires only a catalytic amount of either the photocatalyst or metal mediators because its regeneration is also secured by electrochemistry. At the same time, the proposed methodology provides transient reactive species in small quantities and outside immediate electrode space. This prevents undesired side reactions because formed radicals are frequently more accessible for further oxidation than substrates (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4. EPC-driven C-H activation *via* direct HAT by photocatalyst.

4.1. EPC-Mediated Direct HAT by excited photocatalyst

Lei and coworkers introduced direct EPC-mediated C-H azidation in tandem with Mn-catalysis employing sodium azide (Scheme 5). A series of benzylic **1**, aliphatic **2**, and drug-based molecules with remote C-H bonds were examined for substrate scope.^[21] Comprehensive tolerance was observed, bringing tertiary C-H bonds into the spotlight regarding yield and high regioselectivity. Additional transformation of the prepared azides **3** and **4** into amines provided selective incorporation of nitrogen-based functionality and successful gram-scale synthesis and late-stage diversification, thus suggesting potential applications in preparative synthesis and drug discovery. A simple undivided electrochemical cell was used, using a carbon cloth as anode, to maximize the electrode area which is exposed to light. The reaction could be performed under constant current, as long as sufficiently low current was applied. The proposed mechanism suggests that the azide radical **5** can be formed simply by anodic oxidation. Yet, it is not sufficient for the reaction to proceed as the exclusion of the **Mn(II)/L** complex from the reaction drastically

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influenced the reaction outcome. A detailed mechanistic study indicates that the HAT from the substrate **1** or **2** proceeds by either visible-light irradiated photocatalyst or anodically generated azide radicals **5**. To ascertain which radical species are present in the reaction mixture, experiments with TEMPO as a radical trapping agent were performed. As TEMPO itself can react as an electrochemical mediator,^[22] additional experiments using DMPO as a spin trap were done. This allowed the authors to use EPR for the characterization of the reaction mixture.

Scheme 5. Azidation via direct HAT C-H activation process.

Lambert and coworkers reported EPC-mediated dual C-H heteroarylation of ethers **6** utilizing TAC^+ as the sole electrophotocatalyst (Scheme 6).^[23] Colorless TAC^+ exhibits interesting properties when exploited toward anodic oxidation as conversion into blue radical dication TAC^{2+} occurs, manifesting the aminyl radical cation character, and its subsequent photoexcitation enables the HAT process. The rigid structure of the catalyst $[\text{TAC}^{2+}]^+$ facilitates high regioselectivity resulting from steric differentiation of chemically similar C-H bonds. The proposed heteroarylation was implemented to construct new C-C bonds in reaction with *N*-heteroarenes **7**.

Similarly to the previous case, an undivided electrochemical cell was in combination with a large surface made of carbon felt as anode, leading to successful reaction. Cell voltage was kept constant during the reaction. Due to the broad absorption band of the TAC^{2+} species,^[24] irradiation with a broad-band CFL source was appropriate for this reaction. In addition, the methodology showed compatibility with alkenes or alkynes **8** to furnish alkylation or alkenylation adducts. Furthermore, the use of azoles

9 in the C-H heteroarylation of ethers **6a** was conducted nevertheless with an unresolved mechanism, suggesting two possible reaction pathways.

Scheme 6. C-H activation of ethers by EPC via HAT process.

Ravelli and coworkers described the EPC-mediated dual C-H heteroarylation strategy by cross-dehydrogenative coupling of non-activated aliphatic alkanes **13** with benzothiazoles **14** using a tetrabutylammonium decatungstate **TBADT** (Scheme 7),^[25] which is already known to be competent in driving HAT processes.^[26] Interestingly, platinum gauze could be used as anode in this setup. While much more costly than the carbon felt used in other examples, platinum gauze can be easily cleaned after the reaction, and it does not undergo corrosion during the course of the reaction, allowing the authors to reuse the same electrode. What is noticeable here is that using a divided cell drastically enhanced the outcome of the reaction, and the reaction had to be done under potential control, using a three electrode setup, otherwise a significant drop in yield occurred. Detailed mechanistic studies observed the catalyst's versatile properties, exhibiting a three-fold role as the photo-, electro-, and photoredox catalyst. Most importantly, laser-flash spectroscopy was used to uncover the role of the catalysts in the key HAT step. The substrate scope evaluated a series of selected H-donors **13** and benzothiazoles **14**, which gave medium to very good yields.

Scheme 7. Decatungstate in the role of catalyst for electrocatalysis enabling C-H activation.

4.2. EPC-Mediated HAT in Tandem With a co-Catalyst

Scheme 8. EPC-Mediated HAT in tandem with asymmetric copper catalysis.

Xu and coworkers presented in their pioneering work the first combination of electrophoto- and asymmetric catalysis in enantioselective EPC-mediated C-H cyanation (Scheme 8).^[27] Electrochemical setup for this reaction was undemanding, as the

undivided cell could be used under galvanostatic conditions, and using high-surface RVC foam anode. On the other hand, the source of irradiation was absolutely critical in this case, as only narrow-band irradiation with near-UV LEDs led to success. Broad-band sources (CFL) as well as irradiation with visible light or more energetic UV led to negligible yields, as other species in the system can absorb these wavelengths and induce unwanted reactions. The stated process consists of two relay catalytic cycles in tandem with an anthraquinone-based photocatalyst **AQDS** that site-selectively cleaves the benzylic C-H bonds in sequence with a chiral bisoxazoline-copper catalyst **LCu(II)(CN)₂** by enantioselective C-C bond formation. The formation of the asymmetric center is not affected by the electro- and photochemical steps, and thus the enantioselectivity of this reaction was not influenced by the parameters of the cell. The introduced method proceeds through electron-transfer mediated C-H bond scission, in contrast to the commonly employed C-H cleavage provided by HAT, which minimizes side reactions. Latter sequential electron and proton transfer proceeds through the formation of an exciplex **[AQDS^{•-}16^{•+}]**, which is heavily dependent on the electron density of the employed benzene ring in the substrate **16**, with subsequent proton transfer. Thus, an excellent site selectivity distinguishes between benzylic C-H bonds of similar DBE with a preference for the most electron-rich and sterically accessible benzylic positions, making this protocol compatible with late-stage functionalization of complex structures.

Scheme 9. Riboflavin as photocatalysts in a EPC system.

Lin and coworkers introduced EPC-mediated oxidation of non-activated alcohols **18** in synergy with the riboflavin-derived photocatalyst **RFT** and thiourea **TU** as a co-catalyst acting as a hydrogen atom shuttle (Scheme 9).^[28] To uncover the role of the flavin catalyst, authors have used a Stern-Volmer fluorescence

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quenching study. Flavin-promoted HAT process leads to the formation of the thiyl radical **20** from thiourea **TU**, and this species then abstracts hydrogen from the substrate **18**. Mechanistically, this approach differs from the traditional photocatalytic oxidation with flavin as the catalyst, as the alcohol is activated via HAT instead of SET oxidation. Owing to this difference, the described protocol facilitates a critical expansion of the scope of flavin photocatalysis to substrates beyond those containing electron-releasing substituents that can stabilize key radical or radical cation intermediates accessible by standard photochemical conditions.^[29] From a practical perspective, this reaction is also easy to accomplish, as undivided cell under galvanostatic conditions can be used, with large surface carbon felt as anode.

5. EPC-Induced HAT with Halogen Radicals

5.1. Formation of Halogen Radicals via LMCT

Complexes of iron(III) with chloride can be photolabile, ejecting chloro radical Cl^\bullet upon irradiation (Scheme 10). This phenomenon has been successfully exploited in synthetic processes based on EPC.

Scheme 10. Mechanism of EPC-induced HAT process driven via LMCT formation of halogen radicals.

Collaboration of Noel, Reek, and coworkers introduced EPC-mediated C-H *N*-heteroarylation of ethers **21** and azoles **22** employing a flow setup (Scheme 11).^[30] In this pioneering work, a new *f*-EPC reactor was constructed, enabling light- and electricity-induced processes to occur in the flow. The reactor was composed of a series of stainless steel and PTFE frames in which the serpentine path for the reagents was formed. As for most of the EPC reactions, a large area of irradiated electrode is desirable. This was solved by using a transparent but conductive material as one of the electrodes. In this case, the cathode (counter electrode) was made from transparent fluorine-doped tin oxide coated with a thin layer of platinum to decrease the overpotential for hydrogen reduction. The protocol relies on the catalytic amount of iron chloride complexes that exhibit the ligand-to-metal charge transfer (LMCT) after irradiation, introducing chlorine radicals Cl^\bullet into the system and enabling the subsequent HAT with activated C-H bonds of ethers **21**. Various *N*-containing heteroarenes **22**, such as pyrazole, tri-, tetrazoles, and fused heteroaromatic structures, were well tolerated. Diverse sets of H-donors were successfully conducted in this manner, providing C-H functionalization of α -*N*-, *S*-, or *O*-positions.

Scheme 11. C-H functionalization of ethers with azoles.

Lu and coworkers disclosed a strategy for EPC-mediated C-H alkenylation and acylation of both activated and non-activated alkanes **24** using a pair of redox systems of Ni(II) and Fe(III) as electron shuttles to activate anodic and cathodic reactants in an undivided electrochemical cell (Scheme 12).^[31] Carbon felt was used as both electrodes. Batch EPC reactors mentioned so far generally require cooling as the reaction mixture heats up from the power dissipated by ohmic losses as well as from the light source, and the cooling is usually accomplished by simple fans. In this case, the authors use jacketed electrochemical cells, which allowed them to control the temperature more precisely and cool down the system to -10°C . Similarly, as in the previous example, this protocol relies on the LMCT process of the $[\text{FeCl}_4]^-$ complex, which, after irradiation, facilitates the generation of chloro radicals that provide HAT (anodic process). On the other side, nickel is cathodically reduced, enabling oxidative addition with electrophiles. After another reduction, the Ni(II) complex intercepts the previously formed alkyl radical and furnishes the cross-coupling reaction through reductive elimination. Mono-, di-, tri-, and tetrasubstituted olefins **27** as well as the corresponding ketones **28** were prepared by this methodology using a series of different alkanes **24** as H-donors, alongside with a successful late-stage functionalization and gram-scale experiment.

Scheme 12. EPC-induced HAT process driven via LMCT formation of halogen radicals using tandem nickel catalysis.

Ackermann and coworkers have recently discovered borylation of alkanes, with diboronbiscatecholate as the source of boron. Reaction proceeds under EPC conditions, and the presence of iron(III) chloride has been proven to be crucial for the reaction. While the mechanism is not completely resolved yet,

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there are multiple hints pointing towards chlorine radical, generated *via* LMCT, as the species activating the alkane by HAT.^[32]

5.2. Formation of Halogen Radicals *via* N-X Bond Cleavage

Scheme 13. NCS as a source of halogen radicals for EPC-induced HAT process.

Zha and Wang, with coworkers, developed switchable metal-free EPC-mediated C-H arylation using benzylic H-donors and aromatic nitriles, resulting in diaryl alcohols and diaryl alkanes (Scheme 13).^[33] A simple undivided cell in a Schlenk tube with two platinum wires was used for this reaction, which was performed at galvanostatic conditions. In contrast with the previous example, authors found out that the reaction proceeds with higher yields when elevated temperature (40 °C) is used. This was accomplished by placing the reaction mixture into a hollow metal block with circulating water connected to a thermostat. In this protocol, *N*-chlorosuccinimide (NCS) was used as an accessible mediator that, after visible light-induced homolytic cleavage, provides reactive radical species Cl^\bullet and 29O^\bullet , that promotes HAT. The alteration of the process lies in whether the reaction is exposed to air, resulting in diaryl alcohols **32**, or not, resulting in diaryl alkanes **33** (Scheme 13a). For simplicity, oxygen can react with a benzyl radical **34**, forming a superoxide radical following HAT with subsequent homolysis, providing an alkoxide radical that can undergo radical-initiated β -scission. Another pathway an alkoxide radical can take is oxidation to ketone, depending on stability of the leaving group (Scheme 13b). A combination of kinetic isotope effect measurements with using EPR to study the intermediates as DMPO adducts was used by authors to solve the mechanism.

5.3. Reactions Enabled by Formation of Elementary Halogen

Scheme 14. Generation of Cl radicals by Cl-Cl bond scission leading to activation of C-H bonds by HAT: general mechanism.

Halogens are commonly used as electrochemical mediators, where halogen anion is converted to the elementary halogen on an electrode.^[22] This approach can be coupled with photochemistry, forming reactive halogen radicals capable of inducing HAT (Scheme 14).

Scheme 15. C-H functionalization of aromatic compounds with C-centered radicals generated *via* HAT process with chloro radicals.

Xu and coworkers achieved metal-free dehydrogenative EPC-mediated dual C-H cross-coupling of heteroarenes **35** with aliphatic C-H bonds (Scheme 15).^[34] Authors have used an undivided cell with RVC foam as the anode and platinum as the cathode. Heat from ohmic losses and from light source heated the reaction mixture, and the authors monitored the reaction temperature, but did not attempt to cool it down to room temperature. Interestingly, aqueous HCl was used to decrease the pH of the reaction and facilitate the evolution of hydrogen, leading to better yields than non-aqueous acids, such as trifluoroacetic acid. The proposed method demonstrates wide compatibility with a broad series of heteroarenes **35** and activated or non-activated alkanes **36**. The observed reaction involves a Minisci-type mechanism, where the aliphatic C-H bond undergoes HAT with the chloro radical Cl^\bullet , generated by anodic oxidation of chloride anions with the subsequent light-irradiation-promoted homolytic cleavage of the resultant Cl_2 . Scalability up to the dekagram scale was possible using the flow reactor with recirculation of the reaction mixture through the electrochemical cell.

Scheme 16. Borylation enabled by HAT process with chloro radicals.

The collaboration of Guo, Xia and coworkers introduced metal-free EPC-mediated C-H borylation of various aliphatic C-H bonds exhibiting unconventional regioselectivity, pointing toward distant methyl groups (Scheme 16).^[35] Anodically generated Cl_2 with subsequent irradiation leads to the formation of chloro radicals Cl^\bullet . Such transient radical species undergo HAT with H-donors **38** obtaining the most stable C-centered radical, yet in a reversible manner, which can either isomerize or perform another HAT to gain a less hindered C-centered radical, thus making the reaction with boronate **39** possible. A similar reactor was used as in the previous example, and aqueous HCl was again used as an acid in the system. To find the role of HCl in the system, experiment with a divided cell was performed to show that acid is required only in the cathodic space, where it facilitates the evolution of hydrogen on platinum. Interestingly, phosphoric acid also fulfilled this role, but use of trifluoroacetic acid and triflic acid led to complete loss of efficacy, an unexpected result which was not explained by the authors. In the scale-up reaction, a flow reactor was successfully used.

Stahl and coworkers proposed dehydrogenative metal-free EPC-mediated cyclization via C-H amination of aliphatic amines **41** and imidates **42** in the Hofman-Löffler-Freytag (HLF) reaction (Scheme 17).^[36] In this protocol, iodide was used as an electrochemical mediator in combination with light-induced cleavage of N-I transient species **46**, an example of a decoupled EPC reaction. Reactivity is rationalized by the anodic generation of I_2 , forming a N-I bond with the amine/imidate. Subsequent irradiation of **46** promotes homolytic cleavage of the N-I functionality, forming an N-centered radical **47** that undergoes an intermolecular 1,5-HAT, resulting in a C-centered radical **48**. Radical **48** abstracts iodide from elementary iodine, forming alkyl iodide **49** afterward, leading to the final cyclization. This is a typical example of decoupled EP, as the electrochemically-generated intermediate (iodine) is not activated by irradiation, but instead reacts with the starting material to form a photoactive species, which is activated by light in the second step. Reactions were performed in an undivided cell at controlled potential. Broad-band irradiation by CFL light source was sufficient to drive the photochemical step.

Scheme 17. Hofman-Löffler-Freytag reaction enabled by EPC.

6. C-H Activation Enabled by SET Oxidation of Aromatic Compounds

6.1. Functionalization of C-H Bonds on Aromatic Core

Scheme 18. Mechanism of direct functionalization of arenes by EPC-enabled C-H functionalization.

Electron-rich aromatic systems **50** can be easily oxidized by EPC process. The formed radical cation **51** is then susceptible to further reactions: new electrophilic centers have been formed, attracting nucleophiles to directly functionalize the aromatic core, leading to C-H functionalization process (Scheme 18). The radical thus formed has a strong tendency towards re-aromatization. This can be accomplished by an external hydrogen shuttle such as TEMPO (Scheme 18a) or the photocatalyst itself (Scheme 18b). Finally, the formation of the radical cation **51** can be also accomplished using a photoelectrode instead of a homogenous photocatalyst (Scheme 18c).

Xu and coworkers presented a catalytic EPC-mediated C-H/N-H cross-coupling of arenes **52** with carbamates **53**

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or azoles **54**, which employs **DDQ** as the electrophotocatalyst (Scheme 19).^[37] The proposed method showed good tolerance for a series of mono- and dihalogenated arenes **52**, which are generally challenging to oxidize while maintaining good regioselectivity. The scaleup of this process was also successful. Reaction could be accomplished in a simple undivided electrochemical cell, using RVC foam as anode in a galvanostatic mode. Interestingly, the presence of oxygen had only a minor effect on the yield, even though this reaction utilizes a highly reactive excited doublet catalyst. The intermediate aromatic radical cation **51** could be attacked at any position in this reaction. Authors showed that the regioselectivity could be explained by the shape of the molecular orbitals of this radical cation, which could be readily accessed by DFT calculation.

Scheme 19. Introduction of O- and N-nucleophiles on the aromatic core via EPC-enabled C-H functionalization.

Another example from Lambert and coworkers introduced EPC-mediated C-H heterofunctionalization of arenes **57** subjected in reaction with O- or N-containing functionalities **58** and **59** (Scheme 19).^[38] The suggested protocol provided tolerance for a broad spectrum of substrates, resulting in phenols, aryl ethers **60**, and aryl amides **61**. Reaction setup in this case consisted of an undivided electrochemical cell, with high-surface anode of carbon felt. In contrast with the previous example, reaction was done at a controlled cell potential. The reaction mechanism was similar as in the previous example, leading to a mixture of regioisomers being formed in the process. To scale up this process, a modified continuous-flow system was adapted to a three-channel reactor.

Xu and coworkers introduced EPC-mediated C-H azolation of electron-rich arenes **62** employing a catalytic system consisting of acridinium dye **[Mes-Acr⁺]** and **TEMPO** (Scheme 20).^[39] A simple undivided cell with RVC foam anode could be used for this reaction, under galvanostatic conditions. In contrast with previous examples, where **DDQ** was used as a catalyst, a hydrogen shuttle (**TEMPO**) had to be utilized in this case to accomplish the final aromatization of product **64** (mechanism - Scheme 18a). In contrast to previous examples, this reaction required only a very small concentration of electrolyte (> 10 mM) to proceed efficiently. This is probably due to the ionic nature of the catalyst **[Mes-Acr⁺]** perchlorate, which also acts as an electrolyte. The reaction was compatible with several various arenes **62** and azoles **63**, yet the scope was limited by the reduction potential of the excited acridinium catalyst **[Mes-Acr⁺]**. The second crucial aspect of this process is that the arene **62** coupling partner is oxidized at a potential lower than that of the azole **63**.

Scheme 20. Introduction of azole nucleophiles on aromatic core via EPC-enabled C-H activation.

Lambert and coworkers disclosed EPC-mediated C-H azolation using arenes **62** with **TAC⁺** as the electrophotocatalyst (Scheme 20).^[24] The substrate scope was expanded in this way in comparison with the previous example because of the strong oxidizing properties of the irradiated **TAC** diradical cation. Carbon felt was used as anode, and reactions were performed under controlled cell potential. Cell geometry differed based on what substrate was being converted. Electron-rich substrates could be converted in an undivided cell without problems. Substrates without electron-donating groups on the aromatic ring had to be converted using a divided cell though, and while the selectivity of the process remained good, a portion of the unreacted starting

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material was always isolated when using this setup. Calculations of the properties of $[\text{TAC}]^+$ were also presented to explain its reactivity as a super-oxidant under EPC conditions.

The collaboration of Grätzel, Hu and coworkers introduced an EPC-mediated arene C-H aminoarylation approach using a photoelectrode (Scheme 20).^[40] Haematite photoanode was successfully employed as a replacement for the photocatalyst. The stability of haematite and the heterogeneous nature of electrophotocatalysis in an EPC cell offer potential advantages in catalyst lifetime and product separation. Corrosion of the haematite electrode was negligible, and it could be reused more than 10 times. The proposed reaction with azoles **63** that manifested extended substrate tolerance and, interestingly, exhibited reverse regioselectivity compared to previously mentioned protocols, preferring ortho-positioned sites. The observed regioselectivity was explained by HFIP-provided hydrogen bonding with the radical cation intermediate; however, the functional group as a hydrogen bond acceptor must be present on the arene ring otherwise the regioselectivity diminishes. This unique setup not only allowed for the synthesis of the ortho-substituted derivatives, but it also helped to alleviate a common problem which is present during conventional electrochemical oxidation – electron rich substrates were not over-oxidized, when this setup was used, and a good mass balance (> 85%) has been detected in all cases.

Currently, researchers in this area target more challenging electron-poor aromatic substrates, which are more resistant to oxidation. This requires highly reactive catalysts, which often have a very short life-time, preventing their efficient interaction with the substrates. A successful approach to this problem was devised by Barham and coworkers.^[41] They have developed systems, where catalyst is pre-complexed to the substrate before it absorbs light. This way, even very short-lived excited states can engage in electron transfer and activate arenes for further reactions.

6.2. Functionalization of C-H Bonds in a Benzylic Position

SET oxidation of aromatic core **67** affects the electronic distribution on neighboring carbons. The initial oxidation can be either accomplished by a photocatalyst (Scheme 21a) or by photoanode (Scheme 21b). This initial oxidation leads to the weakening of benzylic C-H bonds in the radical cation **68**. Due to this effect, the acidity of benzylic hydrogens in radical cation **68** is extremely high, and most organic solvents can deprotonate them.^[42] Formed radical **69** is easily oxidized again and finally reacts with nucleophiles (Scheme 21).

Scheme 21. Mechanism of EPC-enabled C-H activation in the benzylic position.

Lambert and coworkers introduced EPC-mediated Ritter-type benzylic C-H amination with acetonitrile (**MeCN**) catalyzed by TAC^+ as an electrophotocatalyst offering a series of acetamides **71** (Scheme 22).^[43] Reactions setup required a divided electrochemical cell, using carbon felt as anode under constant cell potential and broad-band irradiation with CFL light source. Addition of a small amount of water present in the reaction mixture led to an increase in yield, as it is required to hydrolyze the Ritter-type adduct. This protocol is feasible only for unbranched substrates to undergo efficient single-site C-H amination. Its mechanism relies on the oxidation of arene **70** by visible-light irradiated TAC^+ , providing a benzylic radical cation. Subsequent α -deprotonation provides a benzylic radical suitable for another SET. The formed benzylic carbocation proceeds through the classic Ritter reaction with acetonitrile, followed by hydrolysis.

Scheme 22. Ritter reaction on the benzylic position via EPC-enabled C-H activation.

Wu and coworkers introduced EPC-mediated α -N-arene C-H phosphorylation employing an electrophotocatalytic cell (Scheme 23).^[44] Similar photo-redox process is already known,^[45] and the authors aimed to replace the photo-redox catalysis with electric current. They found out that electrolysis with RVC foam anode did also give the product **74** in good yields. They also tested the possibility to use an EPC setup for this reaction and were met with success. The BiVO_4 photoanode was employed in combination with **NHPI** as a mediator. Presence of **NHPI**, which helps to abstract hydrogen from the substrate, was absolutely crucial in this case, with yields dropping significantly in its absence. A similar two-step oxidation process occurs as in the previous example, only facilitated by the presence of a heteroatom. The formed iminium ion finally reacts with phosphonates, forming a C-P bond.

Scheme 23. EPC-enabled C-H functionalization in a benzylic position activated by the heteroatom.

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6.3. Oxidative EPC Leading to Double C-H Functionalization

Lambert and coworkers introduced EPC-mediated vicinal Ritter-type C-H amination of benzylic and adjacent C-H bonds employing TAC^+ as an electrophotocatalyst.^[46] This reaction required a divided electrochemical cell, with carbon felt as anode, under controlled cell potential and broad-band irradiation with CFL light source. In this manner, various arylated *N*-acetyl dihydroimidazoles **76** and oxazolines **77** were prepared in good up to excellent yields. The product formed depends solely on the electrolyte composition. Mechanistically, the Ritter-type process is followed by elimination, resulting in styrene formation that can undergo oxidation into a radical cation and capture another acetonitrile, leading to a final product **76** or **77** after cyclization. To help with the elimination step, the presence of a strong acid (TFA) was necessary, and its replacement with weaker acids led to significant yield deterioration. Due to ambiguous spectral data, authors first suspected that aziridines are produced in the presence of lithium perchlorate electrolyte, but it was proven in the end that the products in this case are the isomeric oxazolines **77**.

Scheme 24. Double Ritter-type process via EPC-enabled C-H activation

The same research group investigated the possibility to modify their protocol to enable multiple oxygenation of benzylic and homobenzylic positions. They succeeded with EPC-mediated multiple adjacent C-H bond oxygenation of alkylarenes **75** and **78** and trifluoroacetamides **79**, employing TAC^+ as an electrophotocatalyst, to their corresponding di- or triacetoxylates **80** and **81**, where the level of oxygenation depends on the choice of acid (Scheme 25).^[47] In particular, this protocol does not suffer from overoxidation and can incorporate up to six consecutive acetoxygenations. In contrast with the previous protocol, undivided cell could be used, and reactions were run under galvanostatic conditions. The reaction mechanism is based on a similar principle as in the previous example. At first, the benzylic position is oxidized and trapped by the nucleophile. After β -elimination, furnishing the styrene adduct, further oxidation occurs,

and the adduct reacts with another nucleophile. The process is repeated multiple times, depending on the substrate properties, C-H bond availability, and reaction conditions. Authors had to carefully select the appropriate acid additive based on the substrate structure. The acid is responsible for the elimination step, the ease of which is influenced by how stabilized is the formed alkene.

Scheme 25. Multiple C-H functionalization with acetate enabled via EPC-enabled C-H activation.

7. C-H Functionalization by Radicals Derived via SET Processes

Photo-redox catalysis can be used to obtain radicals via SET processes on various substrates. Such radicals can be used in a follow-up process to engage in C-H functionalization reactions. This can be combined with electricity in EPC systems, where the electricity acts either as a terminal electron/hole sink from the substrate or to regenerate the catalyst.

Scheme 26. General mechanism for EPC systems, where SET derived radicals react with arenes, followed by oxidative rearomatization by electric current.

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7.1. C-H functionalization with SET-derived Radicals with Electricity as a Terminal Reductant

Xu and coworkers focused on EPC-mediated C-H alkylation of *N*-heteroarenes **83** employing **4CzIPN** as the electrophotocatalyst, resulting in radical decarboxylation of oxalates **84** providing the alkyl radical (Scheme 27).^[48] Another example from Xu and his group uses a similar approach, this time leading to C-H carbamoylation of *N*-heteroarenes **83** employing radical decarboxylation of oxamic acids **86** to provide carbamoyl radicals.^[49] The presented scope suggests broad compatibility with various *N*-heteroarenes **83** and oxamic acids **86** as a carbamoyl source. In both cases, a simple Schlenk tube was used as an undivided electrochemical cell, with large-surface RVC foam as anode under galvanostatic conditions. In the second example, authors studied the effect of different electrode material on the reaction outcome. They have found out that when RVC anode was replaced with a graphite stick, the yield as well as conversion diminished. This shows the importance of a large electrode surface, which is accessible by light in this type of reactions. On the other hand, replacing the platinum counter electrode with nickel led to decreased selectivity. This is due to the possible reduction of the quinoline ring in an undivided cell.

Scheme 27. C-H functionalization of aromatic compounds using radicals derived by SET processes.

The collaboration of Chen, Liu, Li, and coworkers resulted in EPC-mediated *N*-heteroarene C-H alkylation using *N*-alkyl pyridinium salts Katritzky salt, **88** as the alkyl radical source,

employing Ru(bpy)₃Cl₂ as the electrophotocatalyst.^[50] An undivided cell with RVC foam for both electrodes could be used, but the reaction had to be performed under potentiostatic conditions, using a three electrode setup, with a non-aqueous Ag⁺/Ag electrode as a reference electrode. Attempts to perform the reaction under galvanostatic conditions were unsuccessful, giving very poor yield and selectivity. Authors were able to prepare a broad range of starting materials, **88** from readily available pyrylium salts, making this procedure attractive from a practical point of view. This protocol declares good tolerance to a broad spectrum of substrates, and late-stage functionalization of bioactive molecules and gram-scale synthesis were accomplished. The mechanistic rationale relies on the cathodic reduction of *N*-alkyl pyridinium species **88**, resulting in a persistent radical that can undergo fragmentation and provide alkyl radicals. Formed radicals are trapped by *N*-heteroarene **83**, and the following steps are as in the previous examples (*vide supra*). Authors used HRMS extensively to investigate the structure of the intermediates in their reaction, in order to solve the mechanism.

7.2. C-H Functionalization with SET-derived Radicals with Photocatalyst Recycled by Electricity

Scheme 28. The general mechanism for EPC systems, where SET-derived radicals engage in C-H activation processes, electricity recycles the photocatalyst.

Xu and coworkers wanted to broaden the substrate scope of their protocol from oxamic acid **86** to simple carboxylic acids. When attempting the same oxidative decarboxylation with 4CzIPN as in the previous example, only poor selectivity was observed. A large improvement came when they replaced the photo-redox catalyst with CeCl₃ as the photoactive species. With this approach, they introduced EPC-mediated decarboxylative C-H alkylation of *N*-heteroarenes **83** with alkylcarboxylic acid **90**, giving good yields of the cross-coupling product **91** (Scheme 29).^[51] A visible-light irradiated complex of carboxylate and Ce(IV) species, provided by anodic oxidation, leads to the decarboxylative alkyl radical formation.

Other examples from Xu and coworkers disclosed alternative EPC-mediated C-H alkylation of *N*-heteroarenes **83** with organotrifluoroborates **92** employing an acridinium-based electrophotocatalyst [Mes-Acr⁺].^[52] The mechanism relies on the oxidation of organotrifluoroborates **92** by electrophotocatalyst providing alkyl radicals following the steps described in the previous examples. Reaction setup consisted of an undivided cell with RVC foam as the anode. Authors tested the influence of the current density on the yield. As expected, increased current densities led to a drop in yield. But interestingly, no deterioration

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of selectivity was observed, and the starting material remained unreacted after these attempts. This can be rationalized, as in an undivided cell with a reversible redox-active species such as the catalyst **[Mes-Acr⁺]** present in the system, an unproductive redox cycle between the electrodes can be established.

Scheme 29. C-H functionalization reactions of radicals derived via SET with photo-redox catalyst. Electricity is used to recycle the photocatalyst.

Ackermann and coworkers published work on EPC-mediated arene C-H trifluoromethylation employing an acridinium-based electrophotocatalyst **[Mes-Acr⁺]**.^[53] Trifluoromethyl sulfonates (CF₃SO₂Na) were used as the radical source, with CF₃ radical being formed after oxidation with excited photo-redox catalyst. Thus, the formed radical then reacted with arenes or heteroarenes **83** or **84**. Leading to trifluoromethylated products **95** and **96**. To solve the mechanism of this reaction, the authors used real-time monitoring of the reaction system with ¹⁹F NMR.

The collaboration of Shi, Liang, and coworkers realized EPC-mediated tri- or difluoromethylation of alkenes **96** followed by arene C-H functionalization via cyclization (Scheme 30).^[54] This procedure employed eosin Y as the electrophotocatalyst that provides trifluoromethyl radicals from trifluoromethylsulfonates after irradiation. The mechanism relies on trapping the trifluoromethyl radical by a double bond, resulting in another radical followed by cyclization and rearomatization. Reaction setup is a simple undivided cell, and the reaction can be run under galvanostatic conditions. Interestingly, the authors observed a dramatic difference between two similar electrode materials, when they screened the reaction conditions. A commonly used RVC foam electrode performed very poorly as

anode, while after replacing it with a carbon cloth, the reaction proceeded smoothly.

Scheme 30. C-H functionalization/cyclization reactions of radicals derived via SET with photo-redox catalyst.

8. Summary and Outlook

EPC has already demonstrated its strength in the activation of small organic molecules via C-H functionalization. The combination of the energy of light with the electric potential brings together enough power to facilitate reactions of molecules that were out of reach of previous methods relying solely on photochemistry or electrochemistry. Importantly, even non-functionalized alkanes were successfully used in EPC reaction systems, demonstrating the high reactivity and selectivity of the EPC approach. For EPC to realize its full potential, there are still tasks that need to be tackled. Electrochemistry and photochemistry require special equipment and relied on homebrew reaction systems in their infancy. Their full adoption by members of the broader organic community came only with the introduction of standardized commercial reactors. The same will be true with EPC, and developing a “black box” EPC reactor – a commercially available device which will not require any special technical knowledge, and could be simply set up and operated by organic chemists that were never exposed to electrochemistry or photochemistry before. EPC reactions also often require many chemical components; cutting down on their number would make these reactions greener. Electrochemistry has already demonstrated that in thin layers in flow, no electrolyte is needed for electrolysis^[55] and the introduction of such reactors will certainly also come to EPC systems. The final demonstration of the capabilities of EPC will come with its industrial adoption. While many issues with scaling up EPC reactors still need to be resolved, reactors operating at a multigram scale in the laboratory show that this path is not unrealistic.

Acknowledgments

Funded by the European Union (ERC, CAPELE, 101078608). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Keywords: electrophotocatalysis • C-H functionalization • electrochemistry • photochemistry • catalysis

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Electrochemistry and photochemistry join forces in the booming field of electrophotocatalysis. Electrophotocatalytic activation is suitable to engage even previously inaccessible compounds in C-H functionalization reactions. Herin we provide an overview of recent developments in this field.

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